

VARIABILITY IN ISRAELI EDUCATION SYSTEM

Fairoz KHATEEB

Teacher in Israeli Education system

PhD student, Ion Creanga State Pedagogical University

0000-0002-0215-6530

Israeli education system is not a homogeneous one- it is divided to a wide variety of types, sectors and streams. Surveys show that the vast majority of young people have little or no contact with other ethnic or religious groups. This paper points out challenges of heterogeneity and variability in education system of Israel. The society is heterogeneous and consists of Jewish majority, Arab minority and many sub-groups of both populations. A divided school system as well as residential segregation leads to lack of respect and understanding for the “other.” Surveys show that the vast majority of young people have little or no contact with other ethnic or religious groups. In the authors’ opinion, these challenges should be addressed in the future. To ensure that all students in Israel have access to quality education, Israel can work further to ensure comprehensive implementation of its evaluation and assessment framework. Israel needs to respond as well to the increase in student population at all levels of education.

Keywords: *Israeli education system; variability in Israeli education system; divided society; divided schools.*

INTRODUCTION

Israeli education system is not a homogeneous one- it is divided to a wide variety of types, sectors and streams [2]. To improve transition to the labour market, Israel needs to expand and strengthen its provision of vocational education and training (VET). It also needs to ensure quality education in a school system that has grown significantly, with changes in the composition of the student population. Facing a lack of qualified teachers in all subjects, Israel needs to attract quality candidates to the profession and further improve teaching conditions.

To ensure that all students in Israel have access to quality education, Israel can work further to ensure comprehensive implementation of its evaluation and assessment framework. Israel needs to respond as well to the increase in student population at all levels of education. Large differences in performance and education attainment exist between Jewish-ultra-orthodox and Arab students and their peers in the other streams [2,5]. This paper deals with existing challenges of variability of Israeli education system.

STRUCTURE OF ISRAELI EDUCATION SYSTEM

The education system in Israel is steered by the central government, through the Ministry of Education, the Ministry of Finance and local governments. In the last decades, the schools became more independent, however still the structure of the education system did not change much: the Ministry of Education determines education policy, especially in primary and secondary schools, while upper secondary schools are the responsibility of local governments. Expenditure on educational institutions as a percentage of GDP (for all educational levels combined) is above the OECD average, with a higher share of private funding than the OECD average [2].

Israel's education system consists of six years of primary education, six years of secondary education (divided into three years of middle school and three years of upper secondary education) and three to five years of higher education. Pre-schooling includes one compulsory year of kindergarten, which is state funded, and two years of pre-schooling, for the most part state funded. Education is free and compulsory through 12th grade. The following figure describes a structure of the education system of Israel (starting from elementary school) [1]:

Figure 1. Structure of Israeli education system. [1]

GAPS IN PUPILS' PERFORMANCE IN DIFFERENT POPULATION SECTORS IN ISRAEL

Israel has large gaps in educational performance among student population sub-groups, with a heterogeneous system and a relatively large dispersion of socio-economic and cultural background of students between schools and within schools. Although they aim to promote cultural diversity and recognize students' needs, tracking, grouping and school choice practices may increase inequities and contribute to social segregation of students if not well-managed. To improve transition to the labour market, Israel needs to expand and strengthen its provision of vocational education and training (VET) [2,5]. It also needs to ensure quality education in a school system that has grown significantly, with changes in the composition of the student population. Facing a lack of qualified teachers in all subjects, Israel needs to attract quality candidates to the profession and further improve teaching conditions. To ensure that all students in Israel have access to quality education, Israel can work further to ensure comprehensive implementation of its evaluation and assessment framework.

Israel needs to respond as well to the increase in student population at all levels of education. Large differences in performance and education attainment exist between Jewish-ultra-orthodox and Arab students and their peers in the other streams [1]. For example, 51.3% of 18-year-old Jewish-ultra-orthodox students completed upper secondary education in 2013 (compared to 98.2% in other Hebrew-speaking education streams) and 9.0% obtained the secondary school leaving certificate (matriculation) that allows entry to higher education (compared to 72.2% of those in other Hebrew-speaking education streams). Students in Arabic-speaking schools also have lower educational attainment: in 2013, 82.2% completed upper secondary education and 45.7% obtained the matriculation. Enrolment of Arabic-speaking and Jewish-ultra-orthodox students in higher education is below the national average, although participation has increased in recent years (Jewish-ultra-orthodox enrolment in higher education rose from 34.0% in 2008 to 51.3% in 2013, while Arabic-speaking enrolment rose from 76.8% in 2008 to 82.2% in 2013). As discussed below, primary and secondary schools are divided into four separate systems, secular Jewish (defined as Hebrew speaking “state” schools), religious Jewish, “ultra-orthodox” (Haredi), and Arab (defined as native Arabic speaking). The word “Haredi” means “fearing” or “trembling” and reflects the belief by this community in the centrality of religious belief based on the Torah and its rabbinic interpreters. “Ultra-orthodox” is the term commonly used by outsiders to describe the Haredim although it is considered derogatory by the community. The word “Haredi” (plural “Haredim”) is used in the rest of this paper. The Ministry of Education is responsible for school curricula, educational standards, supervision of teaching personnel, and construction of school buildings. Local authorities are charged with school maintenance as well as acquisition of equipment and supplies. The richer local authorities supplement state funding. Teaching personnel at the kindergarten and primary school level are ministry employees, while those in secondary schools are employed by local authorities, which receive funding from the Ministry according to the size of the school population. School principals are responsible for pedagogical issues in their schools and, especially in secondary

schools, play a significant role in selecting staff. Nearly all elementary and secondary schools are public or publicly financed. Over the last few decades, the government has allowed considerable diversity in the actual provision of schooling, with many schools acting to some extent as “charter” schools. At the secondary level, non-governmental organizations are often contracted to play a role in managing schools. Attendance is by catchment areas for primary schools in the desired stream, although parents often find ways to circumvent this regulation, and by parental choice in secondary schools. A national completion examination, the “Bagrut,” is given in the last two years of secondary education. National diagnostic testing (the “Meitsav”) is given in selected primary and lower secondary grades [2].

The author analyzed Israeli pupils’ PISA grades from 2015. This database consisted from results of 6,594 Israeli pupils, both Hebrew and Arab speaking, not including the Ultra-Orthodox sector [3]. The following table presents the highest correlations (Spearman) coefficients between different variables and the math grade, from the highest to the lowest:

Table 1. 2015 PISA tests results. The highest correlations (Spearman) coefficients between different variables and the math grade, from the highest to the lowest [elaborated by the author based on [3]

Israel: Variable	Coefficient
Positive:	
Index of economic, social and cultural status (WLE)	.372**
Index highest parental education in years of schooling	.302**
Environmental Awareness (WLE)	.256**
Learning time (minutes per week) - <Mathematics>	.236**

Home possessions (WLE)	.216**
ICT Resources (WLE)	.168**
Disciplinary climate in science classes (WLE)	.191**
Students' expected occupational status (SEI)	.168**
Negative:	
ICT available at School Index (Sum)	-.283**
Environmental optimism (WLE)	-.272**
Perceived Feedback (WLE)	-.271**
Out-of-School Study Time per week (Sum)	-.246**
Use of ICT at school in general (WLE)	-.178**
Collaboration and teamwork dispositions: Value cooperation (WLE)	-.148**
Personality: Test Anxiety (WLE)	-.128**

As table 1 demonstrates, wealthier families and more educated parents will bring to higher math grades of children. The more possession the family has, especially ICT (information and communication technology) resources, the better the grades will be. However, ICT available at school are negatively correlated with grades.

The following Box-plot histogram shows that the math grades in the Arab sector are lower than the ones of the Jewish sector:

Figure 2. Box-plot histograms of PISA math grades in Hebrew and Arab sub-samples of Israel [elaborated by the author based on [3]]

Definitely, the Arab language pupils are characterized by lower index than the Hebrew speaking pupils (the majority), which brings about the issue of inequality and variability in Israeli education system.

DIVIDED SOCIETY, DIVIDED SCHOOLS

Israel's population in 2014 was estimated at 8.4 million, of which 6.3 million (74.9%) was Jewish, 1.7 million (20.7%) Arab Muslim, Christian, or Druze, and 366,000 (4.4%) classified as "other." The number of Haredim is estimated at 9-10% of the population [1,2]. These social, religious and ethnic divisions are reflected in Israel's education system, which consists of four separate and distinct streams in primary and secondary education. Israel is not the only country in the world with separate school systems, which are common in many multi-cultural societies, especially in those in which there is little separation between the state and the predominant religious denomination in the country [2].

Public state "religious" ("mamlachti dati") schools, serving religious but not Haredi Jews, account for 13.9% of enrollment in primary edu-

cation, down from 14.5% a decade ago. These schools follow the same general curriculum as secular schools, but also include additional intensive religious study. Students come from observant (“modern orthodox” or “religious Zionist”) families following traditions such as Kashrut and Shabbat. Many students also come from what are called “traditional” families (usually “Mizrachi,” originally immigrants from Arab countries) which are less observant [2]. By law, the state must make religious schooling available to parents on demand, a situation that, in small communities, leads to smaller schools and lower student/teacher ratios. Public Arabic-speaking schools enroll 24.9% of primary students, up from 24.6% in 2000. These schools serve Muslims, Christians, Bedouin, and Druze [1,4]. The language of instruction is Arabic, although Hebrew is taught as a subject. They have been historically underfunded compared to Jewish schools, mainly because of higher student ratios as well as lack of financial resources in Arab municipalities. Recent efforts have redressed much of this discrepancy. Nearly all teachers are Arab. The curriculum, except for language and religious studies, is nearly the same as that of Jewish schools. Because of declining birth rates and increased attendance in Jewish schools, Arab school enrollment will decline and go down as a percentage of total primary school enrollment.

A divided school system as well as residential segregation leads to lack of respect and understanding for the “other.” Surveys show that the vast majority of young people have little or no contact with other ethnic or religious groups [2,4]. Along with 29 other countries, Israel participated in the 2000 IEA Civic Education study of knowledge and attitudes of eleventh graders with regard to citizenship, democracy, national identity, etc. Not surprisingly, the study found major differences between Arabs and Jews in pride in Israel’s achievements, history, national symbols, rights of Jewish immigrants, and the legitimate uses of military power [2,3,6].

Arab students were also less likely than were Jewish students to identify the strengths of, and threats to democracy, and had lower levels of efficacy, trust, and support for “altruistic” patterns of citizenship. Several studies have identified negative stereotypes by Jewish students towards Arabs, although these attitudes change depending on the status of re-

gional conflicts. The President of Israel, Reuben Rivlin in 2014-2021, has expressed deep concern with increasing levels of intolerance in Israeli society [2]. He and others have argued that intolerance and loss of confidence in the “social contract” could endanger the viability of Israel’s future existence. A survey by the Pew Research Centers documents the large gaps in attitudes towards and relations with “the other” between the different ethnic and religious groups. A movie, “Teaching Ignorance,” graphically pictures the one-sided explanations of Israel’s history by Jewish, Israeli Arab, and Palestinian teachers. A 2016 review by the Auditor General’s office observed that the Ministry of Education’s programs to build bridges between the different sectors of society were uncoordinated and inadequate to the task and teachers were not properly trained.

REAL QUALITY OF LEARNING ACHIEVEMENTS

Israel’s public had long been led to believe that Israel was a leader in educational achievement, based on the international testing programs in which it participated in 1967 and 1970, when Israel scored the highest in the world among 12-15 participating countries [2]. However, beginning in 1999, Israelis were shocked to discover that their students were doing much more poorly than they were expected. These tests include PISA (Progress in Student Achievement), managed by the OECD, which measures literacy, mathematics, science, and other skills of 15-year-olds, and TIMSS (Trends in Mathematics and Science Study), managed Psychometricians believe that the tests of the 1960’s and 1970’s did not have adequate oversight of sampling frames, and that Israeli Arabs as well as immigrants who had arrived less than two years before were not included in them [3,6]. Therefore, the impression that in the past “things were great” cannot be objectively confirmed. Nonetheless, from 1999 to 2009 Israel scored 50-70 points below the international mean (which now includes a number of developing countries), behind nearly all OECD countries, with the exception of Turkey and Mexico, and lower than expected given its per capita income and the amount of money it spent per student. These tests are based on an international mean of 500 and a “standard

deviation” of 100. Country scores range from a high of 560-600 to a low of around 330. Half a standard deviation in scores is often considered the equivalent of a grade year [3].

Successive governments and ministers of education began to realize that primary and secondary educations were in crisis and initiated a wide variety of programs to raise standards as well as teacher salaries, morale, and quality. The efforts were made by improved scores in the assessments of 2011 and 2012. In the 2011 TIMSS mathematics test given to eighth graders, Israel raised its score by 53 points, landing 6th in the world instead of 24th four years earlier. Israeli Arabs also improved their scores, which are now higher than any other Arab country, although still significantly lower (three quarters of a standard deviation) than Israeli Jews. Israel’s increase in its scores from one test to the next was one of the highest in the 45-year history of the TIMSS assessment. Israel improved its scores in the 2012 PISA, although it still ranks below the average for OECD countries [2]. Israel’s efforts largely used a best practices approach, including focusing on higher order learning skills encouraging teachers to work together, increased hours of study, and more effective pedagogical practices. These efforts have had results of such magnitude that they were highlighted in a 2014 OECD publication on PISA results [3]. Performance in the PISA and TIMSS tests of 2015 showed flat or modestly declining results. This is likely a result of the lowered emphasis on academic achievement by the Minister of Education over the period of 2013 to 2015 [3,6].

SUMMARY

This paper points out challenges of heterogeneity and variability in education system of Israel. The society is heterogeneous and consists of Jewish majority, Arab minority and many sub-groups of both populations. A divided school system as well as residential segregation leads to lack of respect and understanding for the “other.” Surveys show that the vast majority of young people have little or no contact with other ethnic or religious groups. In the authors’ opinion, these challenges should be addressed in the future.

References:

1. ABU HILAL, M. (2017). Far from being equal, Israel's Arab citizens face discrimination in education. Available at: <https://www.middleeastmonitor.com/20170628-far-from-being-equal-israels-arab-citizens-face-discrimination-in-education>
2. EDUCATION POLICY OUTLOOK ISRAEL. OECD. (2016). Available at: <http://www.oecd.org/israel/Education-Policy-Outlook-Country-Profile-Israel.pdf>
3. OECD, PISA 2015 Database. (2015). Available at: <chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.oecd.org/pisa/pisa-2015-results-in-focus.pdf>
4. PIRLS (2001). International Report, IEA's Study of Reading Literacy - Achievement In Primary School in 35 Countries. Shavit, Y., Bolotin-Chachashvili, S., Ayalon, H., and Menahem, G., (2002), Diversification, Expansion and Inequality in Israeli Higher Education, Tel-Aviv University, Oxford Meeting of RC28, April 10-13.
5. TIMSS-R: Third International Mathematics and Science Study. Available at: [https://www.isbe.net/Pages/Third-International-Mathematics-and-Science-Study-\(TIMSS\).aspx](https://www.isbe.net/Pages/Third-International-Mathematics-and-Science-Study-(TIMSS).aspx)